

A New Method of Inversion of Geometrical Isomers by an Exothermic Reaction: Conversion of Maleic into Fumaric Acid.

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The mutual conversion of geometrical isomers or geometrical inversion has been effected both by physical and chemical agencies. Transformation of this character was first observed with fumaric and maleic acids and later on with citraconic and mesaconic, oleic and elaidic, angelic and tiglic, cinnamic and *allocinnamic* acids and other geometrical isomers. Physical agencies such as sunlight (Paal and Schulze, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 168), heat (Tanatar, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 1365), etc., and chemical reagents, specially small amounts of halogens (Wislicenus, *Ber.*, 1895, 23, 1080 2693) or halogen hydracids, as a rule, transform the labile isomer into the stable one. Ultraviolet light (Stoermer, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4865 and subsequent papers) also is known to effect inversion of the stable into the labile modification.

The exact mechanism of the transformation has not yet been definitely established. It was Wislicenus ("Raumliche Anordnung der Atome," Leipzig, 1889) who first tried to solve the problem. He explained the inversion brought about by chemical agents by assuming that the agent at first formed an additive derivative with one of the isomers and was subsequently removed. But later on this view has been shown to be untenable by Anschutz, Fittig, Michael and Skraup (*Monatsh.*, 1891, 12, 108).

Later on Skraup has shown most strikingly (*Monatsh.*, 1891, 12, 107 and subsequent papers) that neither sulphur dioxide nor hydrogen sulphide alone is able to transform maleic into fumaric acid but that a mixture of the two will bring about the transformation. Based on this experimental result, Skraup suggests that an exothermic reaction such as the combined action of sulphur dioxide and hydrogen sulphide in a solution of the isomer acts catalytically in setting up vibrations which he compares to the physical phenomenon of resonance or the chemical effect of an explosion wave, or in other words the chemical reaction between the hydrogen sulphide and sulphur dioxide may be regarded as a type of detonator which starts the transformation in the maleic acid.

Up till now no further experimental work in support of Skraup's theory had been advanced. The present paper adds further experimental support to Skraup's work. Whilst searching for different exothermal reactions which would cause inversions we have found that neither sulphur dioxide nor manganese dioxide can alone transform maleic acid into its geometrical isomer, but when sulphur dioxide is passed into a solution of maleic acid in which finely divided manganese dioxide is suspended the conversion of maleic into fumaric acid takes place most readily in a few minutes. This would be a very interesting addition to the solitary case of the interaction of sulphur dioxide and sulphuretted hydrogen causing inversion as discovered by Skraup.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Maleic acid (1.5 g.) was dissolved in water (5 c. c.) and taken in a long hard glass test tube and purified sulphur dioxide was passed into the solution for more than an hour. No precipitate separated and on evaporating in a vacuum desiccator the residue left was entirely maleic acid (m. p. 130°). Therefore no inversion took place.

The same experiment was performed with manganese dioxide instead of sulphur dioxide at the ordinary temperature and it was found that no inversion took place.

1.5 Gm. of maleic acid were then dissolved in 5 c. c. of water in a long hard glass test tube. 2 Gm. of manganese dioxide well pulverised in a mortar were suspended in the aqueous solution of maleic acid and sulphur dioxide was passed into it. Gradually the temperature of the solution rose from 27° (room temperature) to 60°. The gas was passed for about *five minutes*. Gradually a white precipitate was thrown out of the solution. By this time almost the whole of the manganese dioxide went into solution. Then the white precipitate together with a little undecomposed manganese dioxide was filtered off, washed with a little water to remove any adhering maleic acid and manganous salts and treated with absolute alcohol which dissolved the fumaric acid leaving manganese dioxide behind. The alcoholic solution was filtered and then evaporated in a vacuum desiccator. The crystals that separated were washed with carbon disulphide, collected and identified to be those of fumaric acid. The substance was insoluble in water and sublimed

at 200°. The ethyl ester of the acid obtained was prepared and its boiling point was found to be 218° which is the same as that of ethyl fumarate. About 50 % of the maleic acid underwent inversion

It is to be noted that the precipitation of fumaric acid was complete within five minutes. If, however, sulphur dioxide was passed for a longer period the precipitate of fumaric acid disappeared and various sorts of manganese were obtained in the solution.

With a view to ascertain the effect of temperature the same experiment with manganese dioxide and sulphur dioxide was carried out in an exactly similar manner, the temperature of the reacting medium however being lowered down to 15° and maintained at that temperature by surrounding the reaction tube with ice water. This time only a 10 % inversion was observed. When on the other hand the temperature of the reacting medium was maintained near about 90°, the percentage of transformation was still 50.¹ This is probably due to an equilibrium being set up between the two isomers.

1.5 Gm. of maleic acid were dissolved in 5 c. c. of absolute alcohol and 2 Gm. of pulverised manganese dioxide were suspended in the solution and sulphur dioxide was passed into it. The sulphur dioxide did not react with manganese dioxide in the alcoholic solution and no heat was evolved. No inversion was observed owing to the absence of any reaction. If, however, the alcohol was diluted with an equal volume of water and then sulphur dioxide was passed, it reacted with manganese dioxide and maleic acid was partially converted into fumaric acid.

The same experiment was carried out with an ethereal solution of maleic acid. There was no reaction between manganese dioxide and sulphur dioxide and no inversion was observed.

With a view to ascertain the effect of the reaction between sulphur dioxide and peroxides other than manganese dioxide, 1.5 Gm. of maleic acid were dissolved in 5 c. c. of water and the manganese dioxide was replaced by powdered lead peroxide, and sulphur dioxide was passed into the solution for more than an hour. There was scarcely any reaction and evolution of heat, and no fumaric acid was found to separate.

Similar negative results were obtained by using barium peroxide.

¹ Blank experiments showed that aqueous solutions of maleic acid do not yield fumaric acid even when evaporated to dryness on a water-bath.

In order to ascertain if the inversion was being effected by the heat of the reaction alone, the effect of the action of water on phosphorus pentoxide in which a very large amount of heat is evolved, was next tried. 1.5 Gm. of maleic acid were dissolved in 5 c.c. of water and taken in a basin and a small quantity of phosphorus pentoxide was sprinkled on the solution. Phosphorus pentoxide went into solution with the evolution of a considerable amount of heat and the temperature of the solution rose to about 60°. It was then cooled. No separation of fumaric acid took place even when the solution was cooled.

The last point that was elucidated was to ascertain if the products, viz., manganese dithionate and manganous sulphate obtained by the interaction of manganese dioxide and sulphur dioxide were the real agents which produced inversion. It will be observed from the following experiments that the reaction products do not cause inversion.

1 Gm. of finely powdered manganese dioxide was suspended in 5 c.c. of water and sulphur dioxide was passed through it for 20 minutes. It was then filtered and the filtrate was poured into an aqueous solution of maleic acid (3 c.c. of water containing 1.5 Gm. of maleic acid). The temperature of the solution was kept at 30° for 5 minutes and no fumaric acid separated from the solution. The maleic acid was recovered unchanged on evaporating the solution in a vacuum desiccator and extraction with alcohol.

In order to ascertain if the reaction product would produce inversion at an elevated temperature, the above experiment was carried out in an exactly similar manner, the temperature of the reacting medium however being raised to 60° and maintained at that temperature for 5 minutes. No fumaric acid was formed, and as before maleic acid was recovered unchanged.

Discussion.

From the foregoing experiments it would be observed that the following facts have been established:—

(1) Neither sulphur dioxide nor manganese dioxide alone can effect the transformation.

(2) When sulphur dioxide is passed into a solution of maleic acid in water in which finely divided manganese dioxide was suspended, conversion of maleic into fumaric acid took place in a few minutes. About 50% transformation took place in 2 or 3 minutes. The mere

presence of the reaction acted catalytically in bringing about the transformation.

(1) When the temperature was maintained at 15° a 10% transformation was observed. On the other hand when the temperature of the reacting medium was maintained at about 90° the inversion was still 50%. Probably an equilibrium had been set up between the two isomers.

(4) Inversion did not take place in ether or alcoholic medium. When however the alcoholic solution was replaced by an aqueous-alcoholic one, partial conversion took place.

(5) Inversion did not take place when manganese dioxide was replaced by barium peroxide or lead peroxide.

(6) No inversion was observed when phosphorous pentoxide was added to an aqueous solution of maleic acid. This conclusively proves that the evolution of heat of a reaction is not the agency to produce inversion but the nature of the reaction plays an important part in the phenomenon.

(7) Inversion does not take place if the *resultant products of the reaction* between sulphur dioxide and manganese dioxide are added to an aqueous solution of maleic acid under the same conditions showing that inversion takes place in the midst of the reaction itself.

The foregoing experimental evidences, *viz.*, that neither sulphur dioxide nor manganese dioxide alone can bring about the transformation of maleic into fumaric acid but that inversion starts immediately when the reaction between sulphur dioxide and manganese dioxide is allowed to go on in the solution of the labile isomer would lend support to the "vibration theory" as postulated by Skraup. It would, however, be safer merely to note that the presence of an exothermic reaction like the one studied in this work, though not in general, might act catalytically in starting the transformation, or in other words this would be another instance of a chemical reaction catalytically influencing inversion in the place of a single catalytic substance like bromine or a halogen acid. Further work on this subject with other geometrical isomers is in progress.

